

Media Culture and Media Usage Practices of the Social Strata

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The project fulfillment over 700 pages represents a participant observation and experimental research upon the stated and the real media consumption of the general media audience's members, sliced to its strata, and of the professional media groups. Only the project is available here. Otherwise are included studies over different ethnic, national, mental and social strata in the United States of America and in the European Union – all in a comparative perspective. The US and the EU, because the media leadership and the universalism of the US and the nearest follower EU. Also the empirical fulfillment of the project gives the answer of the questions how does the media mainstreaming effect affects the general audiences in the countries with different multi – and intercultural models, and how this correlates (positive or negative) or not with the field of media producing in the countries with non-democratic, post-totalitarian or pseudo-democratic systems and one-phylum ethno models.

This project, made with the full support of Tervel Technologies Ltd., has the goals to find, gather, make, decode, analyze and understand:

- What is the correct dosage of the different media contents and media usage?
- Where are the cross-purposes of the stated and the real media consumption of the recipients?
- is there a real media culture and cultural media usage, or everything is only a matter of pretending;

- All of the principles of how the media add or withdraw personal status, rating and image;
- What is the impact of the media upon the human look behavior, sensibility, and social movements?
- Where is the AI on the axis of its own presentation?
- How the professional circles impact the media consumption;
- How the subcultural and the referent groups pre-modify the relations between the persons and the rest, and between the person and the virtuality;
- is there a real virulent media effects over the person alone and person in company, while the media impact passes;
- To what extent the recipients render an account to the beneficiary's policy of the media;
- How goes off the imposing of the matrix of subcultural and marketing behaviors media-ward general audience, and vice versa;
- what are the boundaries of the tolerance and the thresholds of physical, interested and moral sustainability of the recipients towards the definite media contents, and what is their most adequate positioning and arrangement in media program schematization;

- Creation the diagram of the connection between the domestic recipients' conduct, the domestic interior design, and the media usage principles out of habit;
- Perception of the social models and appearance of the media characters by the side of the different strata;
- exiting the social stratum models by using the prestigious or not up to par prestigious media;
- Parameters of dilution of the reality notion;
- simpler media effects upon the population;
- Observation of the short term and the cumulative processes in the social strata, came by the side of the media exactly;
- When and under what circumstances media cause subjections, and how they "eat" civic status or professional positions;
- finding the correlation variables between the media consumption and the sociometric variables of the general audience;
- Distinction of the regular and the preferable media and contents in the different strata;
- Social discipline of the media and media discipline of the recipients inside the interactive informational environment;
- is the media future sags to easy predictable prognostication;
- What is the further social effect of the media double standards?
- Who whom influences and how – between the media fashion users, media stylists and designers, and the market makers; and, are the users only affected;
- How the profit takes up a position versus the social worth, and how they exist together;
- How the media autonomy stands next to- or versus the public diplomacy and the social requirements;
- How the media substitute the public agenda setting;
- How the media create the social competencies and how cause the "cognitive dissonance";
- Why the majority of the media general audience accepts, even doesn't approve something;
- What are the effects of the media plurality?
- What kind of inertia generate the media upon the audience's conduct;
- What is the fashion size of the media seasons?
- is there strongly age-attributed media contents;
- are the media only the technical moderators at the trade with influence of the authorities, became such an authorities solely as their own derivatives;
- Creation of the most proper measurement for the put in pawn variables, liable to research;
- What are the influencing mechanisms of the media channeled influencers and what are the chances of one cogent communication in lack of the classic media environment;
- Themes most beneficial for the media owners next to the regional favourability;
- Media suggestions versus the healthy recipient's logic;
- Meaning of media excellence standards lowering or exaggeration, and impact upon the human impressions, repercussions and reactions.

Methodology:

- 1) Participant observation in real audience's recipients in the presence of media and according to the different media contents;
- 2) Experimental research in:
 - 2.1. Media professional circles
 - 2.2. Media addicted circles

2.3. Media denied circles

2.4. Media moderate users

3) Comparative analyses of the data

3.1. between the social strata

3.2. between the professional and the social circles

3.3. Between the audience's groups, based on subcultural limitations or protracts

3.4. cross – cultural (USA – EU)

The prepositional project predicted variables around the media stable equilibrium, the sustainability borders of media development, and the future of the medialism in its creation, advance, cognition and own or audience's prevention and civic restrictions upon the media channels and media contents. Under medialism concept we understand the media institutional and social frame and condition in stable status – quo. Here is the significance of subject research – mostly in its registration of the existing, but not clear phenomenon in the media – society pair, in the prognostication of their mutual interests and injuries, and something more: media' particular reasons of imposing images and contents, by one side, and by other side – the audience's realizing the tangible media advantages in environment of voluntary and unconscious participation by the majority of the media users.